

Data Organization

Tip 1: Develop Conventions for each Project

**Develop a
System for
Naming Files**

**Establish
a Folder
Structure**

**Document your
Organizational
Plan**

Tip 2: Follow Best Practices for Organizing Digital Materials

File Naming

1. Include critical information in file names like sample numbers, dates, or experiment info.
2. Avoid names that are so long that they become cumbersome.
2. Use underscores to separate information.
3. Do not use special characters or spaces.
4. Use the YYYYMMDD for recording dates.
5. Use ascending version numbers that compliment how computers order files.
6. Do not alter or remove file extensions.

Folder Structure

1. Develop a structure that aligns with your project's design, objectives, and data types.
2. Classify folders according to raw, processed, and analyzed data.
3. Use the same folder structure in different storage locations if you use multiple computers or have multiple team members.
4. Use a maximum of 4 nested folder levels to increase usability and reduce confusion.

Other Recommendations

Adapt your organization when needed and document your plan. Your practices should help you, not hinder.

RDM Homepage

How to Reach the RDM Team

Anyone at univie can reach-out to the RDM team for help. You can reach us at rdm@univie.ac.at or find our webpage at rdm.univie.ac.at.